

Remake Learning Days Festival 2024

Evaluation Report

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The research was carried out at the National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR) Doncaster Health Determinants Research Collaboration (HDRC). To find out more about Doncaster HDRC, visit: [Health Determinants Research Collaboration \(HDRC\) Doncaster - City of Doncaster Council](#)

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1. Executive Summary

1.1 Background

Doncaster is the largest metropolitan borough by area in England with a dispersed population. It also has an industrial past and high levels of deprivation. Of the 316 local authorities in England (excluding the Isles of Scilly), Doncaster is ranked 48th most income-deprived (ONS 2021). These present significant challenges in connecting people, places and businesses to economic and social opportunities.

City of Doncaster Council (CDC) has been funded by the National Institute for Health and care Research (NIHR) to deliver the Health Determinants Research Collaboration (HDRC). The HDRC is a partnership project between CDC, the University of Sheffield and Sheffield Hallam University and represents a significant investment to focus on further growing the Council's capacity to develop and use knowledge within decision-making processes leading to better outcomes for Doncaster citizens.

HDRC objectives are two-fold and interconnected:

1. To ensure enhanced use of research evidence to inform decision-making aimed at improving health and tackling inequalities across all functions and departments.
2. To build capability, capacity and motivation to undertake research and development to address the wider determinants of health across our HDRC.

Opportunities for learning are associated with increased positive well-being (New Economics Foundation 2008). Creating opportunities for more equal access to learning therefore has an important role in addressing the wider determinants of health.

In November 2021 Doncaster hosted the UK's first ever Global Education Leaders Partnership (GELP) event which included a presentation from Gregg Behr, co-chair of the Remake Learning Council and Director of the Grable Foundation from Pittsburgh, USA – a place which has a number of similarities in terms of its socio-economic profile with Doncaster. Remake Learning (RL) as an organisation more broadly represents a network that ignites engaging, relevant, and equitable learning practices in support of young people navigating rapid social, technological change and encourages parental engagement. As part of their wider educational approach, RL have been running an annual festival for well over a decade; aiming to promote educational opportunities for children, families and adults in a fun, engaging, and accessible way. CDC committed to taking forward Remake Learning Days Festival (RLDF) as a concept, recognising its potential to be a key delivery vehicle for advancing Team Doncaster's strategic vision for a city-wide learning ecosystem (City of Doncaster Council 2021b).

Survey data gathered at the inaugural festival in 2023 demonstrated significant success in attracting learners to events. However, the team sought support from the HDRC Doncaster with developing a more robust method of evaluation which can provide an analysis of the impact of the festival on learner engagement in Doncaster.

1.2 Research project aims

To support the Skills Team (which oversees the Remake Learning Days agenda) at CDC to develop and implement an effective evaluation method for the RLDF in order to understand the impact of the festival on engagement with learning opportunities in Doncaster.

1.3 Research questions and methods

Research question: What is the impact of the RLDF on participants' future learning?

Methods

The Skills Team was provided with feedback on their existing survey which they adapted for 2024 and distributed at RLDF events. HDRC embedded researchers conducted qualitative interviews with event hosts and participants and two focus groups with participants. One focus group was held with families and one with adults who had participated in the festival. Focus groups were supported by members of the wider HDRC team from CDC.

1.4 Key Findings

Event Hosts were appreciative of the opportunity to be involved in the festival and very supportive of the aims of the festival to bring learning opportunities to a wider audience of Doncaster residents. The main suggestions for future festivals included exploring opportunities for additional funding for activities and providers, identifying whether the administrative process could be less burdensome, and whether there could be targeted support for families who may face additional barriers in accessing opportunities. There was also a suggestion for developing an overall theme for the festival in collaboration with Event Hosts to create a more unified feel. In particular they emphasised the main impact on learning as:

- the importance of bringing people together,
- the increased awareness of learning opportunities locally,
- the positive impact on confidence and well-being for participants,
- participants' increased interest in pursuing learning opportunities
- the positive benefits for their organisations.

The main suggestions from participants for future festivals included increased promotion of events, more sessions and more local events that are accessible to a greater number of families. They emphasised that the main impacts of the festival were:

- bringing people and families together
- learning new skills and enjoying new experiences
- an increased interest in local learning opportunities
- a positive impact on confidence and well-being for participants.

1.5 Summary

Both event hosts and participants felt that the festival had been well-organised and that sessions were engaging and accessible. They appreciated the broad range of events and activities and being part of an important festival for Doncaster. They felt that it had increased confidence and well-being for participants, raised awareness of local opportunities and

brought communities together. They all expressed enthusiasm for the future of the festival and the development of its success going forward.

2. Introduction

2.1 Background

Doncaster is the largest metropolitan borough by area in England with a dispersed population. It also has an industrial past and high levels of deprivation. Of the 316 local authorities in England (excluding the Isles of Scilly), Doncaster is ranked 48th most income-deprived (ONS 2021). These present significant challenges in connecting people, places and businesses to economic and social opportunities. The Director of Public Health's Annual Report assesses overall health status within Doncaster. In England, Healthy Life Expectancy has been steady over a number of years, however for both males and females in Doncaster, rates have been falling since 2015-17 and Doncaster now reports some of the worst Healthy Life expectancy data in the country (City of Doncaster Council 2023a).

The Council and its Team Doncaster partners are committed to a decade of delivery for residents, communities and businesses guided by Doncaster Delivering Together (DDT) which sets out the Great 8 priorities (Doncaster Council, 2021 a).

The City of Doncaster Council (CDC) has been funded by the National Institute for Health and care Research (NIHR) to deliver the Health Determinants Research Collaboration (HDRC). The HDRC is a partnership project between the City of Doncaster Council, the University of Sheffield and Sheffield Hallam University and represents a significant investment to focus on further growing the Council's capacity to develop and use knowledge within decision-making processes leading to better outcomes for Doncaster citizens.

HDRC objectives are two-fold and interconnected:

1. To ensure enhanced use of research evidence to inform decision-making aimed at improving health and tackling inequalities across all functions and departments.
2. To build capability, capacity and motivation to undertake research and development to address the wider determinants of health across our HDRC.

2.2 Rationale

Opportunities for learning are associated with increased positive well-being (New Economics Foundation 2008). Creating opportunities for more equal access to learning therefore has an important role in addressing the wider determinants of health.

Doncaster faces significant challenges in the attainment of qualifications and skills, as outlined in the City of Doncaster Council Education and Skills 2030 strategy:

“Of 317 Local Authority Districts, Doncaster ranks as the 20th most deprived in terms of attainment of qualifications and skills provision, as measured by the Education and Skills Deprivation measure. 37.6% of our Lower Super Output Areas are in the 10% most deprived nationally. Attainment is therefore a clear and present challenge for Doncaster” (City of Doncaster Council 2021b).

In November 2021 Doncaster hosted the UK's first ever Global Education Leaders Partnership (GELP) event which included a presentation from the co-chair of the Remake Learning Council and Director of the Grable Foundation. Gregg shared his experiences of transforming the educational offer through the Remake Learning programme within Pittsburgh, USA – a place which has a number of similarities in terms of its socio-economic profile with Doncaster. Remake Learning (RL) as an organisation more broadly represents a network that ignites engaging, relevant, and equitable learning practices in support of young people navigating rapid social, technological change and encourages parental engagement.

As part of their wider educational approach, RL have been running an annual festival for well over a decade; aiming to promote educational opportunities for children, families and adults in a fun, engaging, and accessible way. CDC committed to taking forward RLDF as a concept, recognising its potential to be a key delivery vehicle for advancing Team Doncaster's strategic vision for a city-wide learning ecosystem (City of Doncaster Council 2021b).

The festival aims to deliver the following outputs:

- To increase the number of innovative and impactful learning experiences across localities
- To provide opportunities to learn 'outside of the classroom'.
- To increase the number of organisations involved in providing informal learning experiences (including through providing grant funding)
- To provide residents with more information about the learning experiences that are already available to them.
- To increase opportunities for intergenerational learning
- To collect information, we can create a communications network with residents who participated in learning activities, which could be utilised to increase engagement with future opportunities.
- To obtain data and insights that would enable partners to improve the local learning offer.

The festival aims to realise the following outcomes:

- To raise awareness about the varied learning opportunities that are available to people locally
- To raise levels of participation in lifelong learning
- To increase levels of parental engagement in their children's learning
- To develop a more diverse and inclusive network of learning providers
- To shift perceptions about lifelong learning and education
- To improve levels of self-confidence, self-esteem, and wellbeing amongst learners

The first RLDF was held in May 2023 with 80 organisations providing a range of activities and events (City of Doncaster Council 2023b). The feedback from this inaugural event indicated that the festival was successful in facilitating high quality learning events, raising awareness about Doncaster venues and opportunities, creating positive health and wellbeing and generating ideas for further innovation (City of Doncaster Council 2023b). The evaluation was limited in this first year and focused primarily on the collection of survey data. Survey responses from the first festival were relatively low with a total of 121 online survey

completions. They were supplemented by additional qualitative data such as quotes captured by members of the team but overall, the team wanted support with developing a more robust method of evaluation that can be used across each year of the festival, and which can provide an analysis of the impact of the festival on learner engagement in Doncaster.

2.3 Aims and research question

Aim: To develop and implement an effective evaluation method for the RLDF to understand the impact of the festival on engagement with learning opportunities in Doncaster.

Research question: What is the impact of the RLDF on participants' future learning?

3. Research methods

The Skills team distributed surveys to participants who attended the learning events across Doncaster which are reported separately. The research team from HDRC Doncaster undertook qualitative research to gather more in-depth data using case studies of organisations to supplement this work, which is reported here.

3.1 Case-study of three Event Hosts

The Skills team recruited three organisations as case studies to better understand the process of organising and delivering the festival events. Each of the case study organisations were small providers operating within the South Yorkshire region providing learning opportunities as a regular part of their organisation's work. Two were small businesses and one a voluntary and community sector organisation (Event Hosts). Each Event Host provided multiple learning opportunities or events as part of the RLDF. The case study data comprised of an interview with a member of staff from the Event Host and either a focus group or interviews with participants who attended the learning opportunities that they organised. The HDRC Doncaster research team attended at least one event provided by the Event Host to recruit participants to take part in the focus groups or interviews and to distribute participant information sheets and consent forms to those who were interested in taking part.

3.2 Interviews with representatives from Event Hosts

Representatives from Event Hosts were interviewed by the researcher two months after the RLDF had been completed. The interview was semi-structured and contained questions related to the following topics:

- strategies for promotion and recruitment,
- successes and areas for improvement,
- impact on the organisation,
- impact on learners.

One senior representative per organisation was interviewed.

3.3 Focus groups and interviews with participants

In addition to the discussions with Event Hosts, focus groups were held two months after the event with participants to understand:

- their reasons for participation,
- any barriers to participation and
- the impact of the festival on their learning.

Two focus groups were held, one attended by three adult participants and one with three families (one parent per family and a total of five children). Due to difficulties recruiting to a third family focus group, telephone interviews were conducted with a further four adult participants who had attended events as a family. The focus group for the families was participatory and tailored to the age group. This included the use of drawing, post-it note activities and physical movement to indicate views and thoughts about the festival and encourage child participation. An appreciation voucher of £25 was provided to each family or adult participant to thank them for their time. The qualitative research undertaken by the research team was approved by Sheffield Hallam University Ethics reference ER65437819.

4. Findings

The data generated from interviews with the event hosts, interviews with participants and participant focus groups has been analysed thematically and is presented below in two parts 4.1) Event Hosts and 4.2) Participants.

4.1 Event Hosts

Motivation to participate

Event Hosts reported a commitment to meeting the aims of the festival to provide an encouraging and supportive environment for people to access new learning opportunities. They emphasised the importance of families having opportunities to learn together and to access a broad range of activities including art, culture and science in a way which is as accessible as possible and free of charge to participate.

“I think that the remake thing is all about...well-being all these life skills to get people and children to feel positive and want to do whatever they want to do and learn and achieve things in their life” (Event Host).

“I think it’s absolutely amazing that its open to everybody and if you can get to the venue you can take part...I really really liked the fact that it was open to everybody... you could go online and book and come along and there wasn’t any kind of risk to it so yeah I think it was such a fantastic festival and I really liked the whole format of it” (Event Host).

Festival organisation

Event hosts welcomed the effective organisation of the festival with clear communication and guidance on what they were being asked to do in running the sessions. They appreciated the visits from CDC staff to view the activities taking place as well as the offers of support.

“(CDC staff) were always asking me if everything was ok, do you need anything and...was just really supportive” (Event Host).

“(CDC staff) was really good and...shared lots of information and we had like a little meeting online beforehand...” (Event Host).

“They were really good, they sent out exactly what we needed to do and I felt I knew what I was doing and that was really really useful and I thought it was really nice that the team came round as well to check on all the workshops” (Event Host).

There was also a suggestion that a post-event meeting could be useful to offer reflections on how the festival had gone and generate learning for the following year.

It was proposed that the process for taking part in the festival could be improved with a less onerous application process. This was felt to be particularly important for small organisations with limited capacity for additional administrative tasks.

“We don’t have many events like that where we have to fill in a massive form you know if there is an event happening then they tend to have the budget and they then tend to just book us...” (Event Host)

In addition, the process of applying to run an activity causes uncertainty for small providers and could form a barrier for providers in participating. As much notice as possible of the event would also help Event Hosts in planning their work.

“Do I give these workshops times to someone else as obviously we can’t afford to not be booking things in and then turning down other things and then finding out we haven’t got funding?” (Event Host).

Two of the Event Hosts indicated that they face challenges with the limited funding for the delivery of festival events, particularly in relation to the work required to complete the forms, prepare the workshops, promote and manage bookings and any follow-up work which is not accounted for in the budget. In some instances, this did not necessarily reflect recommended rates for work in their field. This was important for organisations as small local providers and would be useful to explore further for future festivals in order to ensure their continued ability to take part.

“I don’t think people realise that we didn’t get paid for that so again that’s hard when you run... a small business” (Event Host)

“We...ended up working for less money than we normally would charge” (Event Host)

Similarly, support with time for the preparation of the workshop materials and resources would also be welcomed. If there is additional resource to provide either pre-prepared packs of forms or administrative support at festival events to assist with the registration process, this would allow providers to focus solely on the delivery of the workshops. While two providers did not report any difficulties with setting up their own ticketing system for events, one provider would have appreciated this to have been done centrally. Event Hosts also however recognised the limited funding available to Local Authorities to run events such as festivals.

The Event Hosts all discussed the benefits of involvement in the RLDF in raising awareness about their work and generating increased opportunities. Event Hosts were positive about the beneficial additional opportunities and support provided by the Remake Learning staff with accessing training and promotional opportunities.

“I was really really honoured that we had been selected to be filmed as part of it and again that helps us as a business that we are in that film we are being shared” (Event Host)

Event organisation and accessibility

The Event Hosts felt that the promotion of the festival in year two was an improvement on year one and that the use of social media campaigns and the festival branding were largely effective in reaching local communities.

“I thought the marketing was a lot better. You always get people saying oh I didn’t know about that but again it’s a new festival” (Event Host)

“I really appreciated...the quality of the social media, they had clearly invested in having proper branding and I thought that (was) great” (Event Host).

Event hosts felt that the majority of participants at events had seen the events promoted on social media particularly Facebook and CDC channels.

“We have noticed a lot of the families, generally and I am talking about our stuff as well do look on Facebook and do look on things to do because it’s linked to the council” (Event Host).

“It was just through Facebook really that people booked on” (Event Host).

The Event Hosts who had ticketed sessions all sold out very quickly and it was felt that there was unmet demand for places.

“They both sold out, really fast” (Event Host).

“I think from the Remake team putting things out, it all sold out so again they have managed to build that reputation of really good stuff happening and people looking out for it waiting to book on” (Event Host).

Ideas for limiting the number of tickets that individuals can book were explored by Event Hosts to ensure more families can attend and to prevent wasted spaces and this may be useful to reflect on further. However, they also recognised that this can be difficult for larger families who may require a greater number of tickets.

Two of the Event Hosts felt that there had been a good age range of participants for their family events and that the activities provided were accessible to children from very young to age 10 or 11.

“So we had a good range from quite little three four right up to ten but that’s because I quite like designing activities that you can do if you are really little and you can do if you are older and you can make it... more sophisticated the older you are which I think is important because obviously a lot of the families that come may have a real mix of ages of kids” (Event Host).

“Because we have a lot of siblings we do end up with a wide range between the ages of five and eleven to be honest and quite a good spread of that age because a lot of people come together with siblings and there tends to be a couple of years between them so yes we did have the full age range really” (Event Host).

One provider felt that the venue and promotion of the activity could have been more tailored to families with children for one of their activities and that it would have been good to have had the involvement of teens although:

“People still came with their mums and their sisters and things so that was nice” (Event Host).

It would be beneficial to analyse the demographic data of participants at the events to consider the diversity of participants as it was difficult for Event Hosts who were unfamiliar with the local population to know if participants reflected the diversity of the area.

“We did seem to have a really good variety of people at the workshops which was...really really nice to see...I think we did quite well with that but again I don’t really know whether that was anything we did...but as I said I don’t really know the demographic” (Event Host).

Importantly, one Event Host reflected on both the barriers to participation for disadvantaged families:

“I think the interesting question is when you think about people who are not engaging in the arts or learning or activities, I think it’s a much deeper-rooted situation where you

have got a lot of families in (place) who are not even aware of that so it's just like they have got so much else going on they are not looking" (Event Host).

and a need for increased promotion to reach a broader diversity of communities:

"The majority of people will be white British, and I think that's an area we are all aware of and needs more work there to try and open things out a bit more and encourage people to come so we are starting to do it but I don't think we are doing it enough" (Event Host).

They suggested focused outreach work with families through linking to schools to reach families that may not otherwise hear about or attend the events. It was also felt that the 'hub' approach to hosting multiple activities in a location may be an effective way to encourage participation.

"My feedback to Remake would be to do more of that so that you have hubs, hubs of activity and then I think you'd get more footfall" (Event Host).

Another interviewee reflected on the focus on social media which may exclude those who do not access information in that way and suggested an increase in other methods of promotion to complement the social media campaigns such as posters in local communities. It may also be beneficial to review the website holding the festival event information to see if this could be simplified to make it easier to view the range of events taking place.

"On the website on remake learning when I looked there were a lot of people that had uploaded events but had repeated ones you know I don't know how many they uploaded, they were like the same thing just a different hour" (Event Host).

One further suggestion was the choice of an overall theme for the festival to increase a sense of being part of a bigger event.

"I think there is something interesting maybe in some of the creatives working together on that so that different things make up a bigger thing. I think there is something quite interesting in that. People quite like that because it means a part of a much bigger more exciting project" (Event Host).

Impact of the Remake Learning Festival

It was felt that the Remake Learning Festival brought positive benefits to the Event Hosts as well as the participants of the workshops. Event Hosts identified four main benefits; 1) the importance of the increased awareness of their organisation and the work that they do, 2) they were able to reach new audiences 3) they have developed new areas of work and 4) they developed links with other organisations.

"I tell you what it has inspired, we talked a little bit about it at (organisation) anyway but because the remake festival was so successful, and we got quite a lot of families. I am running three drop-in family workshops over the summer...so that definitely had a

connection to remake because it just sort of felt like it made us go yeah we should be doing more of this” (Event Host).

“I think it was quite beneficial to us as a company to expand out across South Yorkshire” (Event Host)

“We have just received funding and I think Remake helped us with that because we were approached ...to apply for the funding for the school holidays and obviously I mentioned the success of remake learning and the demand for our workshops” (Event Host).

“So, it has given me that push to start doing new things and trying different kinds of classes” (Event Host).

“We have had people at the classes that haven’t been before so sometimes I expect just the regulars to come but there were a lot of people that have never been before and that’s the best thing about it” (Event Host).

“It’s my own little business...so it’s just anything like this is a brilliant help for small businesses and just getting that recognition and new people and they will come back. We have had funded ones before where we have then got regulars out of it because they love it so much and they have tried it for free and they have been able to pick up a new hobby, make new friends and socialise” (Event Host).

Importantly, Event Hosts also indicated that the events would not otherwise have taken place without the support of the RLDF funding.

“We would have done somewhere else; our main Spring Bank would have been fully booked but we might not have been running them in Doncaster” (Event Host).

“They on that occasion wouldn’t have happened because we weren’t doing anything particularly in that holiday and particularly as we haven’t got any money either” (Event Host).

Event Hosts emphasised the positive impact of the festival on participants in a number of important ways.

“The country is in a challenging situation; things are hard for everybody so just the fact we do small things and then you know I think it makes a difference” (Event Host).

All Event Hosts spoke about the significance of the events being free to attend in order to make them as accessible as possible for those with lower incomes.

“It lets them try it without the pressure of having to spend some money on the ticket so it reaches a wider demographic of people from maybe lower socio-economic

backgrounds in Doncaster that just can't afford it, so it really broadens, it brings a wider variation of people to the events who have maybe never been interested in (the activity) before so yeah, its brilliant" (Event Host).

Activities and events were also seen as a critical way to provide an opportunity to try a new activity and spark a new interest or skill for participants.

"We do have a lot of people who start at our classes and end up really get into (activity) and I follow them on Facebook, and they end up becoming really quite amazing...just from starting and realising that they have got a talent" (Event Host).

Two of the Event Hosts raised the importance of the activities for improving family relationships and increased well-being for participants.

"There are a few ladies that come to the sessions, and they say it really helps with their anxiety and gives them some socialisation with other people without having to actually meet up with other people you can go if you want to chat you can yeah its always really helpful to do these things" (Event Host).

Event Hosts were really positive about the Remake Learning Days Festival and the opportunities that it gave to both their organisation, participants and the City of Doncaster.

"I think remake learning is important and an important festival to continue and I hope it continues" (Event Host).

"I just think it was an absolutely fantastic event and I think everybody involved in organising that should be so proud, what a feat really, it was absolutely amazing and I think they completely hit that target of what was my understanding of the festival was to engage people in activities that they had not done before and to reach all areas of the community. And I think they did that absolutely brilliantly and I think it will just build momentum..." (Event Host).

"These festivals are so important to bring culture and arts and new things to people, so people do have things to do in Doncaster and it becomes a safer, diverse place where people can come and do fun activities and especially family activities as well" (Event Host).

In summary Event Hosts were appreciative of the opportunity to be involved in the festival and very supportive of the aims of the festival to bring learning opportunities to a wider audience of Doncaster residents. The main suggestions for future festivals included exploring opportunities for additional funding for activities and providers, identifying whether the administrative process could be less burdensome and targeted support for families who may need support to access opportunities. There was also a suggestion for developing an overall theme for the festival in collaboration with Event Hosts to create a more unified feel. In particular, they emphasised the main impact on learning as; the importance of bringing people

together, the increased awareness of learning opportunities locally, the positive impact on confidence and well-being for participants, participants' increased interest in pursuing learning opportunities and the positive benefits for their organisations.

4.2 RLDF participants

Motivations

Participants were motivated by a strong desire to try new activities and events. For families the opportunity to be able to spend time together was felt to be particularly important.

"It was for the kids, like I say they love doing things like that. It was getting them out, getting them out of the house we are not a big tv, tablet family anyway so we love getting the kids out and trying different things as well" (participant).

"It was looking for something to do with my daughter... it was looking for something nearby, fun to do and free" (participant).

"I just wanted to do something, I think it's nice to find something to do with my daughter" (participant).

A number of the adults also indicated that the opportunity to socialise in environments and activities which do not rely on alcohol were particularly welcome.

"Like she says the (age group) 20-26 sort of thing they don't want to go out drinking and stuff they want to do pottery painting and different things" (participant).

Event organisation and accessibility

Those who participated in the study reported mixed views on the effectiveness of the promotion of events. It was felt that those who regularly use social media or are signed up to receive news and alerts from the council are more easily able to find out about activities. It was identified that there may be gaps in being able to reach those who do not regularly use those methods. In particular, the use of Facebook was effective in many instances and the majority of those who participated in the study found out about the events through this channel. There was a general view that this needed to be supplemented with additional promotional activity. A number of suggestions were made to expand the promotional strategy of the festival including greater use of existing networks of organisations such as scouts, distributing information through schools and local press and advertising in community venues such as community hubs, gyms, halls, post offices and supermarkets. It was also felt that there were some people who would need to be reached through word of mouth so expanding the knowledge about the festival to a greater audience would be useful to achieve this.

"Everything was online, everybody has got social media. I didn't see anything posted on post office windows and things like that but because my wife does classes with (person) we learnt about it that way but there was a lot on Facebook as well" (participant).

"I saw it on Facebook and I think I have liked the Doncaster council website and page so I think it was probably as part of that so yeah I tend to look out for lots of events" (participant).

"I think there is just so much now that gets promoted on Facebook and I am not on Facebook" (participant).

"I must say with Facebook I have given up with Facebook because it's just adverts after adverts after adverts" (participant).

Participants felt that distributing festival information through school newsletters would be an effective way to reach more families and may also help to diversify attendees at events.

"I don't know whether it gets promoted through schools for instance so school sends out a newsletter for example just to sign post it, with it being over the holiday it might be useful in terms of reaching wider audience. There are people that I mentioned it to that weren't aware that it was on for instance, just might be one to consider" (participant).

"The only thing that I found a lot of people say they didn't know about it and I don't understand how I had seen it everywhere...maybe each of the schools I know we go to school in a little village and they never used to get told about any events to then pass it on you know on their websites maybe that would help" (participant).

"Maybe just like send an online flyer to schools may be to like get more diversity because I do tend to see the same people at events so it's definitely working in that you are getting people coming back at events" (participant).

Increased notice about events and earlier promotion would also be welcomed to allow families to incorporate opportunities into their plans:

"I know there were more places doing it but I didn't know where so like more information on and maybe getting the information out about it earlier so this event is happening on this date at this place and this place so there is more information so parents can plan around if they can access something" (participant).

A good range of dates, times and local venues was identified as useful due to the range in participants needs and lifestyles. Participants talked about how they worked part-time, were shift workers or were retired and so a provision of opportunities on multiple days and times would enable them to be able to more easily be able to attend sessions. Similarly, some participants were happy with the central location of activities which they could access via a local bus route, but others were reluctant to use a central location during the evening.

"I work part-time so it's about them falling on the right days and availability and things like that but yeah if there were other ones nearby, I would go to them" (participant).

“They couldn’t do those particular dates as they are all nurses or healthcare assistants, so they don’t get their shifts in time. They are not sure what they are doing at that time” (participant).

“It was only one bus ride away and my daughter goes to school on a bus route, so we stayed on the bus rather than getting off and went into town, so it wasn’t anything putting us out really” (participant).

“I am always reluctant to do anything in the town centre because it can be rough at night particularly” (participant).

Participants that we spoke to had often travelled to attend sessions.

“I did look local, but I think it was just the (activity) that was close to us and others were in town weren’t they. I think because it was free and because there were different things that were offered, I didn’t mind really where we travelled to” (participant).

It is useful to note that although the Remake Learning Festival was targeted at Doncaster residents it was also attended by participants from outside Doncaster.

All participants found the events they attended to be very welcoming and accessible.

“I didn’t have any barriers to accessing what was there, everybody is so lovely as well” (participant).

“There was clear information about where things were they were both at places where its accessible for everybody. I have a few health needs and that and I felt comfortable going to both these places” (participant).

“I do I think it was relaxing and there was no sort of like competition in it” (participant).

Importantly however the feedback about travel and accessibility was from participants who had been able to attend the sessions and this evaluation does not include feedback from those who did not attend. Some participants did note that more support for families who have not been able to access sessions would be valuable coupled with more local provision and local promotion.

“If you wanted to get good attendance from local people it would be locally” (participant).

“If it was nearby and the kids knew about it” (participant).

“Maybe having some of the broader things that were available at Doncaster library at the smaller sites would have been great...if you couldn’t travel then it might be quite nice to have in the local hubs a bit more options” (participant).

A number of participants commented that they had found it difficult to book on to all the sessions they would like to attend and therefore would have liked more sessions to be available as well as sessions held on different days and times to suit differing work patterns.

“When I went to book, the days I wanted weren’t available” (participant).

“There was just one ticket left and I tried to get two and there was only one so I emailed the email address and just said if anyone drops out can you let me know” (participant).

One participant commented that they had booked a number of places in anticipation of additional friends attending but had unfortunately wasted one ticket as a result as they were unable to attend. Similarly, one participant felt that they had insufficient time to explore all of the activities on offer at the night at the museum event due to the time limitation at that event and others commented that they would have liked the sessions to be longer.

“At the night at the museum we didn’t get around even half of the things in the hour that was allocated because I think we were the first session so obviously just had the first hour at the beginning so we didn’t make it to other things we would have also enjoyed” (participant).

“I totally enjoyed it, and I think if it had been another hour we wouldn’t have got bored, we enjoyed it” (participant).

One participant thought that there had been a possible miscommunication about one of the activities as participants were confused about whether an activity required pre-booking or not. It may be useful therefore to ensure clarity about which activities require pre-booking.

Events and activities

Participants were impressed by the diversity and range of activities on offer as well as the suitability for a range of ages and the skills and knowledge of the event host staff.

“Different things and a massive variety of things and things you wouldn’t expect at that sort of environment” (participant).

“I think what they offered was really good actually, I was really impressed with what was on offer” (participant).

“Just keeping it diverse again there was so much different choice which I feel is good” (participant).

“Near, accessible and a mix of age ranges because that’s sometimes hard you know something for everyone to do and that so yes accessibility. It looked fun” (participant).

They felt that activities were well organised and delivered by supportive staff who were passionate about their area of expertise.

“The lady who was running that was super knowledgeable and really really praising all the time and praising the kids.. My son and daughter both smiled because to hear that from a stranger... and (it) boosted confidence so it was nice to see that as well” (participant).

“I think the people who did the stuff at (place) the one in Doncaster where they did the activities, the crafts and things, those staff there and the people really were absolutely amazing they were really passionate about what they did, they really wanted to be there, they were really engaging with the kids” (participant).

“It was nice the ladies giving their expertise but then also chatting about other stuff and just being really nice to her so it’s like the whole experience was just nice” (participant).

The children and adults really enjoyed the interactive and ‘hands on’ nature of the activities.

“I liked it when it when we had the glue, and we put the dye in” (child participant).

“It was nice to all be able to do it and do it together and it was quite educational because they told us the science around it and it was fun so yeah and we all got involved so that was nice” (participant).

“It’s nice just to chill out and have a good time doing stuff” (participant).

The children particularly talked about the animal encounters, the different animals that they had been introduced to, and the science activities including the slime workshops and light installation. They also enjoyed spending time with family and friends at the sessions.

The ability to be able to access free provision particularly for families who may have a low income was seen as critical.

“The fact that it was free was brilliant” (participant).

“That I think that was really good for people to be able to get into those places because you know if there is more than a few of them it is quite expensive to go to those places” (participant).

“It was just you know the fact that I knew there was something we could do and that we had something there for people you know that may not have a lot of money to go and do stuff the kids got to back to their friends later you know when they went back to school and say to their friends I did this in the holidays and it was exciting... if there wasn’t stuff like this then a lot of children probably wouldn’t get to do stuff... that’s what I thought

were nice just the fact that we could be made to feel welcome, no pressure to do anything but it was there for us to use.” (participant).

“I think it’s nice that money is not an object either you know” (participant).

“A chance to try before you buy” (participant).

The impact of the festival

Participants reported the overall impact of the festival in bringing people together and enhancing a sense of community.

“The whole family enjoyed the day...I took the kids and they just really enjoyed the day and seeing different things and meeting different people from different backgrounds and that’s what communities is. It brings everyone together to enjoy a day” (participant).

“It’s just nice to get people involved again, everyone seems separated don’t they in the last few years they have come apart again you know with covid and it’s just nice to get people back together, smiling us adults as well to be fair I think that’s what good about a lot of these events” (participant).

They also emphasised the importance of having time together as a family.

“It was beneficial for me to spend time with the kids, I have just changed jobs which saw me working nights so having that time with the kids was really beneficial for me, just to sit, listen, watch, no distractions and have fun and see how they are progressing creatively and knowledgably in different ways” (participant).

“I think just spending time together and having a bit of fun really. The main thing was spending time together and having something that we both enjoy doing, keeping kids occupied and just being able to do something fun together” (participant).

Building confidence was seen as a key outcome by many participants whether adults or children.

“It does build your confidence a bit as you think I am not actually as bad as I thought. I can actually do that bit you know when something goes right it feels so good” (participant).

“Just for her she took away that she could be a bit more independent because these events are focused on like obviously you can help if you want but you know encouraging the children to make decisions, to make, they wasn’t talked over, they wasn’t told what to do and left, they could have the support, they could not have the support. It was very child led but in a way that everything was there as well” (participant).

“It has made me think actually after the (activity) that I can do anything, so I have started with Duolingo now and I am learning French” (participant).

“Not to be like so stressed about it straight away, it’s not going to turn out that badly and everyone’s is all different” (participant).

Learning and developing new skills as well as rediscovering past interests were also shared as examples of the impact of the festival.

“Learning how to put the ingredients in” (child participant).

“It was just fantastic to see them in there and having fun and exploring as well” (participant).

“So, it’s good fun, good social interaction for the kids, learning new skills, trying different things, being creative without worrying that you are doing anything wrong as there is no wrong or right” (participant).

“I think particularly the STEM session, I think particularly with that process of sort of making the product and then seeing how it worked...so I think she really enjoyed that, she enjoys crafts but she particularly enjoys making things so that was great” (participant).

“I think the flower bashing was really interesting...just because we then took that away and had a go at that ourselves. We went and picked flowers from the garden and did it, we went over to my sisters and did it with her cousins so that was nice to take it away and something we will probably do that again” (participant).

“I even bought some acrylic paints in a little set...to do at home” (participant).

“I was very excited about the painting, I used to do a lot of artwork...I used to go and paint the backdrops for their stage work” (participant).

The RLDF provided an opportunity to do activities that it would be hard to set up at home:

“As a parent you don’t always have the materials and sometimes it’s having someone else with the expertise to have done the working out for you and guide them through that and with my eldest, she really enjoys almost that teaching element so with other people she will tend to be a bit more focused and a bit more enjoying learning from other people” (participant).

“It’s not something we tend to do at home because one we don’t have a proper garden” (participant).

Participants stated that they are looking for other events to attend and where the festival had generated discussion about other opportunities that may be available to pursue and an increased awareness of other venues in Doncaster.

“We probably will over the summer holidays now they are coming up I will be on the lookout for similar sorts of things that are going on around and about round” (participant).

“I have booked on more as well and my son on the back of it has now booked on the one you pay for, the (name of session) she is doing in September” (participant).

“I don’t think I have had anything through from Remake Learning but I started to follow (venue) on Facebook after that and so we are planning to attend some of the summer events” (participant).

“Drawing attention to kind of other spaces within Doncaster what’s available within those spaces. Just because you are not always sure what is going on everywhere and so it draws your attention, so we now know there are quite a lot of things going on over at (venue) so yeah, I think that has been really really useful” (participant).

d) Suggestions for future activities

Participants made a broad range of suggestions for possible activities that they would like in a future festival. This included a range of sports, games and skills such as ice skating, archery, watersports, walking/hiking, circus skills, traditional games and chess. Dance activities in a range of styles such as adult dance sessions, dance for children and young people and Morris dancing. Music lessons or activities such as drumming or silent discos. Activities including animals such as meet the animal or activities for dog owners. Art based activities such as photography and poetry. Well-being activities such as aromatherapy or gem therapy as well activities such as history, computer-based activities or learning about other cultures.

“My children like learning about other cultures...more arty, more cultural stuff” (participant).

They also however thought that the festival had been diverse and would like more of the same:

“I think just more of the same and I think the craft stuff is really nice you know like the unusual things that they don’t get to do at home and stuff I think that’s really nice for kids and I think it’s good for all ages as well it’s not just necessarily just little kids even the older ones can do it as well” (participant).

“Everything you have done so far is brilliant so anything like that” (participant).

Overall participants were very appreciative of the opportunities provided by the festival, the level of organisation and the commitment and skills of the staff from Event Hosts who delivered the sessions. They also felt that the festival was a great addition to Doncaster as a city.

“We really enjoy those kinds of things and those kinds of sessions and it’s really nice to have that kind of thing in Doncaster” (participant).

“Just thank you for listening and wanting to do more for the community and children and that it’s nice that somebody is there thinking of ways to help them enjoy and have a nice childhood and it’s nice that we don’t feel like we are working on our own” (participant).

“It felt really nice for us, and we were saying that Doncaster seems to miss out on things” (participant).

In summary the main suggestions from participants for future festivals included increased promotion of events, more sessions and more local events that are accessible to a greater number of families. They emphasised that the main impacts of the festival were bringing people and families together, an increased interest in local learning opportunities and a positive impact on confidence and well-being for participants.

5. Limitations

This evaluation is limited by the small number of both Event Hosts and participants who participated in the interviews and focus groups, but the evaluation was able to include participants from a range of ages and circumstances. It would be useful to include further views and experiences from a much broader range of participants and those who have not attended Remake Learning Days events to date. While the view of a small number of children were included, the views of older young people such as teenagers were not.

6. Key insights and recommendations

Key insights and recommendations were proposed which can be investigated for the future development of the RLDF including:

- Exploring the use of an overall theme for the festival with linked events.
- Additional support for event hosts with the administration and/or streamlining the administrative process.
- Identifying additional funding for the delivery of the festival.
- Expanding the promotion of the festival to include more posters, local advertising and school and community networks to complement the social media campaigns.
- Reviewing the accessibility and clarity of information on the event website.
- Targeted recruitment, support and events for families who may face barriers to accessing events.
- An increase in the number of activities.
- The provision of more sessions for each activity.

- More opportunities to access activities in local neighbourhoods.
- Reviewing whether it is possible to improve the booking systems to reduce unused spaces while still ensuring free and equitable access.
- Increasing the variety of sessions to encompass broader areas of learning such as sport, fitness, nature and the environment, music, culture and art.
- Further research with families who may face barriers to accessing events and families who are under-represented in attending events to identify ways in which access can be improved.
- Further research with older children or young people about their engagement and interest with the festival.

7. Summary

Across the Event Hosts and participants there were common themes of the festival's impact on future learning for participants. For many of the participants the festival ignited a further interest in learning and taking part in events. It supported confidence-building with both young people and adults who participated and brought together both families and wider communities. Through this, the festival was able to provide opportunities to socialise and improve well-being and to support parents in Doncaster with enabling children and young people to have fun, develop confidence and access further learning.

Both Event Hosts and participants felt that the festival had been well-organised and that sessions were engaging and accessible. They appreciated the broad range of events and activities and being part of an important festival for Doncaster. They felt that it had increased confidence and well-being for participants, raised awareness of local opportunities and brought communities together. They all expressed enthusiasm for the future of the festival and the development of its success going forward.

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